

1 **Open-population models provide an alternative trout monitoring method in the upper**
2 **Yellowstone River, Montana**

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26 **Abstract**

27 Long-term monitoring programs typically require standardization to evaluate changes in fish
28 populations over time. However, incorporating new methods into long-term monitoring
29 programs may become increasingly important as climate change affects sampling conditions. In
30 the upper Yellowstone River, Montana, biologists have monitored trout abundance using closed-
31 population, Lincoln-Petersen mark-recapture methods since 1978. In the past two decades,
32 changes in the hydrologic regime have prevented monitoring from occurring annually. We
33 investigated the feasibility of individually marking trout and using the POPAN formulation of the
34 Jolly-Seber model to estimate the abundance and survival of three trout species in the upper
35 Yellowstone River as an alternative to historical monitoring methods. When using this modeling
36 framework, annual sampling can be conducted in a reduced time period, allowing monitoring to
37 be adapted to changing environmental conditions. Analysis of a three-year empirical dataset
38 provided estimates of abundance and survival for most sites and species. Simulations indicate
39 that POPAN models produce unbiased estimates of demographic parameters when detection
40 probability is ≥ 0.20 , and precision of estimates increases as detection probability and apparent
41 survival increase. Using POPAN models to analyze mark-recapture data from individually
42 marked fish may provide a feasible alternative for monitoring trout populations in the upper
43 Yellowstone River. Although further evaluation of monitoring methods as data collection
44 continues is warranted, open-population models show promise as a useful tool for monitoring the
45 trout fishery in the Yellowstone River and in rivers across Montana.

46 **Keywords:** POPAN model, Jolly-Seber models, climate change, mark-recapture

47 **Impact statement:** In the upper Yellowstone River, changing hydrologic conditions prevent
48 long-term trout monitoring from occurring in some years. Using POPAN models to analyze

49 mark-recapture data from individually marked fish may provide a feasible alternative method for
50 long-term monitoring of trout populations.

51 **Introduction**

52 Long-term standardized monitoring programs are a vital component of fisheries management
53 (Nichols and Williams 2006; McClelland et al. 2012; Radinger et al. 2019). Long-term
54 monitoring data are typically standardized to allow for comparisons over time (Beard et al. 1999;
55 Bonar et al. 2009); however, monitoring programs may also be adapted as technology, questions
56 of interest, and sampling conditions change (Lindenmayer and Likens 2009). As climate change
57 increases the rate of environmental change, existing monitoring programs may need to be
58 adapted to ensure monitoring data are continuous and relevant to current questions of interest
59 (Lindenmayer and Likens 2009; Lindenmayer et al. 2011). Adaptations to monitoring programs
60 may include adopting new sampling methods and incorporating new technologies or analytical
61 techniques.

62 Standardized monitoring of trout populations has been occurring in the upper Yellowstone
63 River, Montana, since 1978, following the methods used to monitor trout populations in large
64 rivers across the state. The monitoring program, conducted by Montana Fish, Wildlife & Parks
65 (MFWP), consists of annual electrofishing mark-recapture surveys in the spring to estimate
66 abundance of nonnative Rainbow Trout *Oncorhynchus mykiss* and Brown Trout *Salmo trutta*,
67 and native Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout *Oncorhynchus virginalis bouvieri* (recently reclassified
68 from *O. clarkii bouvieri*; Page et al. 2023) using batch marking and Lincoln-Petersen population
69 estimates. However, obtaining Lincoln-Petersen population estimates is becoming increasingly
70 difficult due to changes in the timing and duration of spring snow-melt runoff (Lamborn and
71 Smith 2019; Hostetler et al. 2021). Specifically, warming spring temperatures cause river

72 discharge to increase from base flow conditions to peak runoff conditions more quickly, resulting
73 in a reduced window to conduct spring mark-recapture sampling, because electrofishing is
74 infeasible at high discharge conditions and ineffective at base flow conditions (Lamborn and
75 Smith 2019, Briggs et al. 2024). Electrofishing at base flow conditions in early spring or late fall
76 has been considered as an alternative sampling approach but was found to be ineffective because
77 high water clarity allows fish to see approaching boats and feel the approaching electrical field.
78 Fish are able to escape capture, resulting in few fish captured and low capture probabilities.
79 Although electrofishing at baseflow is often effective in other western rivers, including in
80 Montana, it is not suitable for trout monitoring in the upper Yellowstone River. Recapture
81 sampling must be conducted within one to two weeks of the marking sample to meet the
82 assumption of a closed population and to avoid sampling during periods when trout are
83 spawning. In some years, discharge conditions prevent recapture samples from occurring and in
84 other years, neither marking nor recapture samples can be conducted, preventing MFWP from
85 obtaining annual trout abundance estimates (Opitz 2021). The loss of continuity in the long-term
86 monitoring data is particularly concerning for MFWP with regard to Yellowstone Cutthroat
87 Trout, which are a focus of conservation efforts throughout the upper Yellowstone River
88 watershed (Endicott et al. 2013).

89 Maintaining continuity while adapting monitoring programs is an important consideration
90 when implementing new analytical or sampling methods (Lindenmayer and Likens 2009).
91 Previous research investigated the feasibility of using two alternative analytical methods, N-
92 mixture models and mean catchability, to estimate trout abundance in the upper Yellowstone
93 River using the historical, long-term dataset (Briggs et al. 2024). Unfortunately, both analytical
94 methods investigated were unsuitable for reliably estimating trout abundance in the upper

95 Yellowstone River (Briggs et al. 2024), therefore new sampling and analytical methods must be
96 developed. Evaluating new sampling methods often involves implementing new methods while
97 continuing historical methods to facilitate comparison, which can add considerable cost and time
98 to monitoring programs. Thus, determining if the additional effort and expense is justified should
99 be evaluated.

100 The standardized protocol for trout monitoring in the upper Yellowstone River was
101 adapted by individually marking trout instead of batch marking trout. Mark-recapture data can
102 provide more information when animals are individually marked than batch marked (Williams et
103 al. 2002). When analyzed using an open-population modeling framework, such as a Jolly-Seber
104 model, mark-recapture data with individually marked animals can be used to estimate multiple
105 parameters to describe population dynamics, including abundance, survival, and recruitment
106 (Jolly 1965; Seber 1965; Williams et al. 2002). Monitoring vital rates such as survival and
107 recruitment in addition to abundance can reveal the processes underlying changes in population
108 abundance, providing biologists with important information to guide management (Gowan and
109 Fausch 1996; Osmundson and White 2017). Additionally, many open-population models provide
110 more sampling flexibility than closed mark-recapture models, and annual abundance can be
111 estimated with a single sampling event per year or when data are insufficient for closed-
112 population abundance estimates (Schwarz and Arnason 1996; Williams et al. 2002; Shroyer and
113 Hodgins 2024). In the upper Yellowstone River, using open-population models to analyze mark-
114 recapture data with individually marked trout may provide an alternative to historical monitoring
115 methods, allowing MFWP to maintain consistent monitoring under changing environmental
116 conditions while also improving our understanding of trout population dynamics.

117 Here, we assessed the feasibility of using the POPAN formulation of the Jolly-Seber
118 model to estimate the abundance and survival of trout in the upper Yellowstone River using
119 mark-recapture sampling with individually marked fish. We used a short-term, empirical dataset
120 and a series of simulations to determine if open-population mark-recapture models will be an
121 effective alternative to closed-population mark-recapture models for monitoring trout
122 populations in the upper Yellowstone River. Our research questions were (1) Can we estimate
123 abundance and survival of all three trout species in the upper Yellowstone River using POPAN
124 models? (2) Are the abundance estimates from POPAN models biased when compared to those
125 from closed-population models? (3) How do varying, simulated values of abundance, survival,
126 and detection probability influence the accuracy and precision of parameter estimates from
127 POPAN models? The results of this research will identify standardized monitoring methods that
128 can be used to evaluate the status of trout populations as environmental conditions change in the
129 upper Yellowstone River and across Montana.

130 **Methods**

131 *Study area*

132 The Yellowstone River originates in the Bridger-Teton National Forest in northwestern
133 Wyoming and flows 1,114 km to the confluence with the Missouri River in western North
134 Dakota (Figure 1). It is the longest unregulated river in the contiguous United States. The
135 hydrologic regime of the Yellowstone River is snowmelt-driven, with a large peak in discharge in
136 the late spring during runoff. The study area consists of two long-term sampling sites, Mill Creek
137 and Corwin Springs, located between Gardiner and Livingston, Montana (Figure 1). The length
138 of the Mill Creek sampling site is 7.13 km, and the length of the Corwin Spring sampling site is
139 6.57 km. At the sampling reaches, the Yellowstone River varies from approximately 50 to 90 m

140 in width and 1 to 5 m in depth. The upper Yellowstone River drainage supports a valuable
141 recreational trout fishery that contributed an estimated \$70 million to the local economy in 2013
142 (Sage 2016).

143 *Field sampling*

144 Electrofishing was conducted annually by MFWP biologists in late April and early May
145 when Yellowstone River discharge and turbidity conditions were favorable for electrofishing,
146 typically at flows between 56 and 142 m³/s. One to three electrofishing samples were conducted
147 annually at each site, and samples were completed over a period of one to eight days at each site.
148 Electrofishing was conducted using one or two jet boats or drift boats mounted with boom
149 electrofishing equipment; variation in sampling equipment was a result of variable
150 environmental conditions. Boats were each equipped with a Smith Root VVP-15B and a Honda
151 generator (Opitz 2021) and had one or two netters. Average output amperage was standardized
152 between 2.5 and 3.0. Each sample consisted of electrofishing along both riverbanks. When two
153 boats were available, the two boats would electrofish along the left and right banks
154 simultaneously; when one boat was used, electrofishing along each bank occurred separately
155 over one or two days. Each fish was identified to species, measured to the nearest 2.5 mm
156 following MFWP standard protocol, and implanted with an 8-mm passive integrated transponder
157 (PIT) tag (Biomark, Boise, ID) in the dorsal musculature. The adipose fin of each fish was
158 clipped to assess tag loss. If a fish had already been tagged during a previous sample, the tag
159 number was recorded.

160 *Empirical data analysis*

161 Capture histories were compiled for all individual fish sampled during the three-year
162 study period. Capture histories for all samples conducted within a year were collapsed into a

163 single event for each year, resulting in capture histories with three occasions for each individual.
164 A detection indicates the individual was captured at least one time in the given year, while a non-
165 detection indicates that the individual was never captured in the given year. We used the POPAN
166 formulation of the Jolly-Seber model (Schwarz and Arnason 1996) to estimate the
167 superpopulation size (N), apparent survival (ϕ ; the probability that an animal survives and
168 remains in the study area between sampling occasions), detection probability (p), and probability
169 of entry (b ; the probability that an animal from the superpopulation (N) enters the population
170 between sampling occasions). Annual abundance (N_t) was obtained as a derived parameter and
171 was divided by the length of the site to estimate the number of fish per kilometer. The POPAN
172 model assumes that catchability is the same for both marked and unmarked individuals,
173 individuals retain their tags during the study period, survival probability is the same for both
174 marked and unmarked individuals and temporary emigration does not occur (Williams et al.
175 2002). Each site and species combination were modeled separately to avoid
176 overparameterization. Twelve models were fit to the dataset for each site and species. Phi (ϕ)
177 was either allowed to vary freely over time or held constant over time; p was either time-varying,
178 constant, or modeled as function of fish length; and b was either time-varying or constant. The
179 twelve models represented all combinations of ϕ , p , and b . Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)
180 was used to compare among models. No environmental covariates were considered in the
181 analysis due to the short time series of the empirical dataset. All models were fit using Program
182 MARK (White and Burnham 1999) implemented in R version 4.3.1 (R Core Team 2023) using
183 the RMark package (Laake 2013). Model fit was assessed using the R package R2ucare
184 (Gimenez et al. 2018).

185 When possible, we also used a Chapman-modified Lincoln-Petersen estimator to estimate
186 the abundance of the three trout species at each site to maintain continuity with the long-term
187 standardized monitoring data. Lincoln-Petersen abundance estimates were obtained when
188 multiple electrofishing surveys were conducted at a site in a single year and when the final
189 survey occurred approximately six days after the previous survey. The initial survey or surveys
190 were used as the marking event, and the final survey was used as a recapture event. The six-day
191 period between surveys allowed marked fish to mix with unmarked fish but was short enough to
192 assume that the population was closed to losses and additions. During the recapture event, fish
193 were considered recaptures if they had been sampled during the marking survey in the same year
194 only. At Mill Creek in 2021, sampling consisted of a single day marking sample and a single day
195 recapture sample, separated by a gap of six days. At Mill Creek in 2022, MFWP conducted two
196 consecutive days of marking sampling and no recapture sampling; in 2023, two consecutive days
197 of marking sampling were followed by a six-day gap and a single day recapture sample. At
198 Corwin Springs, single day marking and recapture samples, separated by six days, were
199 conducted in 2021. In 2022 and 2023, two consecutive days of marking occurred but no
200 recapture samples were conducted.

201 Lincoln-Petersen abundance estimates were obtained using the `mrClosed()` function in the
202 FSA package in R (Ogle et al. 2023). Estimates were divided by the length of the site to estimate
203 the number of fish per kilometer. The Lincoln-Petersen abundance estimates were compared to
204 annual abundance estimates from the POPAN models using relative bias, calculated as the
205 difference between POPAN and Lincoln-Petersen estimates divided by the Lincoln-Petersen
206 estimate. Although both Lincoln-Petersen and POPAN estimates may exhibit bias, Lincoln-
207 Petersen estimates have been used historically, so they were treated as a baseline here.

208 Additionally, new monitoring methods should be compared to historical methods to ensure
209 continuity of long-term datasets (Lindenmayer and Likens 2009).

210 *Simulations*

211 Simulations were used to assess the performance of POPAN models. Simulations provide
212 the opportunity to assess the accuracy and precision of model estimates and explore the utility of
213 the models over a longer period and a wider range of possible scenarios than represented in our
214 empirical dataset. The use of simulated datasets allowed us to compare model estimates to
215 known (simulated) abundance, apparent survival, detection, and probability of entry values. We
216 simulated 10-year datasets using varying values of N , ϕ , p , and b . Simulated values of ϕ , p , and b
217 for each year were obtained from distributions, representing annual variation in parameter values
218 over the simulated 10-year dataset. We selected 16 scenarios to represent combinations of
219 differing N , ϕ , and p . The combinations consisted of two levels of N , two levels of ϕ , and four
220 levels of p . Values of N and ϕ were based on the empirical estimates of abundance and apparent
221 survival from the Yellowstone River obtained using POPAN models to approximate a range of
222 realistic scenarios. Values of p were selected based on empirical estimates from this analysis and
223 from historical estimates of electrofishing capture probability (Briggs et al. 2024). N was either
224 10,000 or 20,000 individuals. Apparent survival was obtained from a beta distribution with a
225 median of either 0.3 ($\alpha = 6$, $\beta = 14$, standard deviation = 0.32) or 0.7 ($\alpha = 14$, $\beta = 6$, standard
226 deviation = 0.32) representing low and high ϕ scenarios. Detection probability was obtained
227 from a uniform distribution with a median of 0.10 (bounds = 0.05, 0.15), 0.15 (bounds = 0.10,
228 0.20), 0.20 (bounds = 0.15, 0.25), or 0.25 (bounds = 0.20, 0.30) representing extremely low, low,
229 moderate, and high p scenarios. Probability of entry was obtained from a Dirichlet distribution
230 with $K = 10$ and all values of α equal to 10 ($\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{10} = 10$). A Dirichlet distribution is a

231 multivariate generalization of the beta distribution; using a Dirichlet distribution to simulate
232 values of b constrains values between 0 and 1 and produces a vector of b values that sum to 1
233 ($b_1 + b_2 + \dots + b_K = 1$). Datasets were simulated using the `simul.js` function in R adapted from
234 Kéry and Schaub (2012). A single POPAN model was fit to each dataset where ϕ was allowed to
235 vary freely over time, p was held constant, and b was allowed to vary freely over time. Holding p
236 constant over time reduced the occurrence of confounded parameters in the model output and
237 allowed us to more fully examine how changes in p influence accuracy and precision of model
238 estimates. We simulated 1000 iterations of each scenario.

239 We examined estimates of N , N_t , ϕ , p , b , and the standard errors associated with each
240 estimate to identify outliers, which indicated unsuccessful parameter identification. Iterations
241 where any parameter estimate showed indication of unidentifiability (i.e., standard error = 0)
242 were removed from further analysis (Table S1). To assess accuracy of model estimates, we
243 calculated the relative bias of each estimated parameter as the difference between the estimated
244 and simulated values divided by the simulated value. We used the 80% quantiles to assess the
245 spread of relative bias, which indicates the range of relative bias associated with each parameter
246 in each scenario. To assess the precision of model estimates, we examined standard error. Annual
247 abundance and apparent survival are of greatest interest to fisheries management because these
248 parameters can be used to evaluate changes in fish populations over time; therefore, we focus on
249 estimates of annual abundance and apparent survival.

250 **Results**

251 *Empirical data analysis*

252 Over the duration of the study, 4,265 individual trout were tagged. In the Mill Creek
253 reach, 1516 Rainbow Trout, 927 Brown Trout, and 238 Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout were tagged.

254 In the Corwin Springs reach, 512 Rainbow Trout, 532 Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout, and 540
255 Brown Trout were tagged (Figure 2). Of the fish tagged in the Mill Creek reach, 8.5% were
256 recaptured at least one time in a subsequent year. In the Corwin Springs reach, 6.4% of the
257 tagged fish were recaptured at least one time in a subsequent year (Figure 2). The smallest fish
258 included in the study was 109 mm and the largest was 640 mm; 90% of the fish sampled were
259 between 196 and 465 mm in length (Figure S1). Tag loss was observed in 20 individuals (0.45%
260 of tagged fish). Due to the low rate, tag loss was not considered further in the analysis.

261 Apparent survival, detection probability, and abundance were estimated for all sites and
262 species using POPAN models with all parameters held constant, except for Yellowstone
263 Cutthroat Trout at Mill Creek (Figures 3 and 4). Assessment with the R2ucare package did not
264 identify problems with model fit. Including time-varying parameters in POPAN models resulted
265 in unidentifiable parameters for all sites and species, so results from models with time-varying
266 parameters are not reported. For all sites and species, AIC scores showed equal support ($\Delta AIC <$
267 2) for the model with constant ϕ , constant b , and constant p and the model with constant ϕ ,
268 constant b , and fish length as a covariate for p . The all-constant model was the top model for all
269 species at Corwin Springs and for Rainbow Trout at Mill Creek. The model including fish length
270 as a covariate was the top model for Brown Trout at Mill Creek ($\Delta AIC = 0.46$). Evidence for
271 including fish length as a covariate for detection probability was moderate, so we selected the
272 most parsimonious model for each site and species, and we report estimates from the all-constant
273 models.

274 Estimates of apparent survival varied by site and species and were higher at Mill Creek
275 than Corwin Springs (Figure 3A); however, confidence intervals overlapped among all estimates.
276 Estimates of detection probability varied from 0.12 for Rainbow Trout at Mill Creek to 0.32 for

277 Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout at Corwin Springs (Figure 3B), however, confidence intervals
278 overlapped among all estimates. Annual recruitment to the population (including immigration)
279 was lowest for Brown Trout at Corwin Springs and highest for Rainbow Trout at Mill Creek
280 (Figure S2). Lincoln-Petersen abundance estimates were obtained for the Mill Creek reach in
281 2021 and 2023, but only in 2021 at Corwin Springs (Figure 4). Estimated detection probabilities
282 from Lincoln-Petersen estimates varied from 0.13 to 0.30, depending on year, species, and site.
283 Annual abundance estimates from the POPAN models were higher than those from the Lincoln-
284 Petersen estimator for all sites, species, and years when comparisons were possible. Out of the
285 seven possible comparisons in annual abundance estimates, four comparisons had overlapping
286 95% confidence intervals (Figure 4). However, the 95% confidence intervals for the POPAN
287 annual abundance estimates were broad, and the Lincoln-Petersen abundance estimates had
288 narrower confidence intervals (Figure 4). Relative bias was highest for Rainbow Trout at Mill
289 Creek with values of 4.23 in 2021 and 2.35 in 2023. Relative bias was also > 1 for Brown Trout
290 at Mill Creek in 2021. Relative bias was < 1 for all other sites and species and varied from 0.02
291 for Brown Trout at Corwin Springs in 2021 to 0.64 for Rainbow Trout at Corwin Springs in
292 2021.

293 *Simulations*

294 Median relative bias was near zero (between -0.1 and 0.1) for annual abundance and
295 apparent survival in all scenarios, indicating that POPAN parameter estimates were not
296 consistently negatively or positively biased (Table 1, Figure 5). However, the spread of relative
297 bias varied by parameter and scenario, indicating the possibility for larger bias in scenarios with
298 low or extremely low values of detection probability and low values of apparent survival (Table
299 1, Figure 5). The 80% quantiles of relative bias for annual abundance estimates were between -

300 0.25 and 0.25 for five scenarios, all of which had moderate or high values of detection
301 probability and four of which had high values of apparent survival (Table 1, Figure 5A). For
302 apparent survival, the spread of relative bias was lower in scenarios with higher values of
303 detection probability and apparent survival (Table 1, Figure 5B). Standard error for annual
304 abundance and apparent survival declined as detection probability and apparent survival
305 increased (Table 2). Estimates of other parameters (N , p , and b) showed similar patterns with
306 lower relative bias and higher precision at moderate and high values of detection probability
307 (Tables S1, S2, Figures S3 – S5).

308 **Discussion**

309 By individually marking trout in the upper Yellowstone River, we obtained annual
310 estimates of abundance and apparent survival for most sites and species, including in years when
311 Lincoln-Petersen abundance estimates were not possible due to a reduced sampling period.
312 Precision was low for all estimates; however, low precision is expected with only three years of
313 data, and we surmise precision will increase with additional years of data. Additional years of
314 data collection may also make estimation of parameters possible for Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout
315 at Mill Creek. Due to the limited timeframe, all parameters were held constant in the analysis to
316 allow models to converge and to reduce the occurrence of confounded parameters in model
317 output (Schwarz and Arnason 1996). However, holding all parameters constant over time does
318 not represent a realistic monitoring scenario, because the goal of monitoring programs is to
319 assess changes to populations and demographic rates over time (Lindenmayer and Likens 2010).
320 Despite the limitations of analyzing the three-year dataset, assessing the feasibility of open-
321 population models for trout monitoring is important. Individually marking trout in the
322 Yellowstone River adds cost to annual monitoring and increases the time required to complete

323 each electrofishing survey, so it was important to determine if continuing to expend the
324 additional effort and expense will be useful in future years. Thus, we chose to analyze a short-
325 term empirical dataset to allow managers to make informed decisions about the future of trout
326 monitoring within an appropriate timeframe.

327 Continuing to evaluate estimates obtained from POPAN models and considering the use
328 of covariates in the future will be useful as data collection continues. The two methods produced
329 similar abundance estimates for some sites and species (e.g., Brown Trout and Yellowstone
330 Cutthroat Trout at Corwin Springs), but abundance estimates were highly variable for other sites
331 and species (e.g., Rainbow Trout at Mill Creek). The variation in abundance estimates from the
332 two methods warrants further evaluation. Additionally, the abundance estimates from the POPAN
333 models were less precise than the Lincoln-Petersen abundance estimates, which may pose
334 limitations for assessing trends and communicating results to the public. Comparison with
335 historical methods is an important component of evaluating alternative monitoring approaches
336 and ensures that the continuity and integrity of the long-term dataset is maintained (Lindenmayer
337 and Likens 2009, 2010). However, due to low sample sizes, the comparisons between empirical
338 POPAN and Lincoln-Petersen mark-recapture abundance estimates provide limited information
339 for fully assessing the performance of POPAN models in our system and further evaluation is
340 warranted. In addition to continued evaluation, including covariates in addition to fish length to
341 model detection probability may be useful for obtaining time-varying estimates of other
342 parameters. Covariates may include turbidity, water temperature, or the number of annual
343 surveys conducted at each site (Speas et al. 2004; Korman and Yard 2017).

344 Jolly-Seber models provide more information than closed-population models, which only
345 provide estimates of annual abundance and detection probability. In the Yellowstone River,

346 results from the POPAN models represent the first empirical estimates of trout apparent survival.
347 Apparent survival estimates represent the probability that trout survive and remain in the
348 sampling site, and thus the estimates incorporate information about both mortality and
349 movement. The additional information on population dynamics obtained from open-population
350 models is useful in a range of management applications. POPAN models have been used to
351 assess the demography of endangered or imperiled species to determine if populations are stable
352 or declining (Tezanos-Pinto et al. 2013; Ford et al. 2022; Rohner et al. 2022). Information on
353 population dynamics and long-term abundance obtained from POPAN models can also be used
354 to assess the effects of management actions and guide future conservation (McDougall et al.
355 2017; Glassic et al. 2020). POPAN models were also used to obtain abundance estimates of
356 Muskellunge *Esox masquinongy* in a Minnesota lake when data were insufficient for closed-
357 population abundance estimates (Shroyer and Hodgins 2024). In the Yellowstone River, current
358 trout monitoring focuses primarily on annual abundance estimates, but the estimation of
359 additional demographic rates using POPAN models, or other types of Jolly-Seber models, may
360 be useful for assessing responses of trout populations to environmental and anthropogenic
361 stressors in the future.

362 Simulations are an important tool for assessing analytical methods, including accuracy
363 and precision (Pine et al. 2003; Carroll et al. 2015). Results indicate that parameter estimates are
364 not consistently positively or negatively biased, although the spread of relative bias varied by
365 parameter and by scenario. When median simulated values of detection probability were below
366 0.20, the relative bias of parameter estimates was more variable, indicating that low detection
367 probability increases the chance of biased estimates. It is recommended that values of detection
368 probability in mark-recapture studies are at least 0.10 to obtain reliable estimates, and higher

369 detection probabilities will result in improved precision (Otis et al. 1978). Estimates of detection
370 probability from the empirical data analysis were above 0.20 for Brown Trout and Yellowstone
371 Cutthroat Trout and 0.19 for Rainbow Trout. Long-term mark-recapture data from the
372 Yellowstone River indicate that detection probabilities ≥ 0.20 are attainable (Briggs et al. 2024);
373 however, consistently achieving a detection probability ≥ 0.20 will likely require multiple,
374 consecutive days of electrofishing. Obtaining parameter estimates will still be possible if
375 environmental conditions prevent multiple surveys from occurring in a given year, but precision
376 will be reduced and the possibility for bias will be greater.

377 Standard error associated with apparent survival and annual abundance estimates was
378 lowest when simulated values of detection probability and apparent survival were high. Higher
379 detection probability results in a larger mark-recapture dataset, providing more information for
380 estimation. Higher simulated apparent survival represents conditions where a higher proportion
381 of fish survive and remain in the study area, resulting in higher recapture rates. Although
382 detection probability can be increased through sampling effort and methodology, apparent
383 survival is a characteristic of the trout population. Thus, if apparent survival of trout in the
384 Yellowstone River is low, as indicated by empirical estimates at the Corwin Springs site, the
385 precision of parameter estimates may be lower than desired. Additional years of data collection
386 will improve empirical estimates of apparent survival for trout in the Yellowstone River and
387 provide a better understanding of how apparent survival influences parameter estimation using
388 POPAN models.

389 Simulations can increase inference about model assessment, particularly when empirical
390 datasets are limited (White and Cooch 2017). We selected the 16 scenarios to represent a range
391 of possible conditions based on our limited, empirical data. However, simulations do not

392 represent all possible scenarios that may be encountered. Using simulations also required
393 selecting the annual variation associated with each parameter. The variation in our simulated
394 parameter values may be higher or lower than true variation in demographic parameters of trout
395 populations in the upper Yellowstone River, which may cause discrepancy between the results
396 from our simulation study and future empirical estimates of vital rates.

397 Our results suggest that individually marking trout and analyzing the results in an open-
398 population model framework may provide a feasible and flexible alternative to closed-population
399 mark-recapture models for trout monitoring in the upper Yellowstone River, Montana. POPAN
400 models do not require multiple sampling occasions each year. Multiple surveys can be conducted
401 to improve detection probability, but they can be conducted on consecutive days, allowing
402 sampling to be completed within a reduced period. However, limitations associated with using
403 open-population models for trout monitoring do exist. Environmental conditions occasionally
404 prevent any sampling from occurring in the upper Yellowstone River. Although POPAN models
405 can produce estimates for years in which no sampling is conducted, the precision is likely to be
406 low and occasional gaps in monitoring data are still possible. Additionally, individually marking
407 trout with PIT tags increases the cost associated with trout monitoring and the time required to
408 complete each survey. Given that monitoring trout populations in the upper Yellowstone River is
409 a high priority for MFWP and the ineffectiveness of the current closed-population monitoring
410 protocol, the increased cost associated with open-population monitoring is justified. Adapting the
411 standardized monitoring program for trout in the upper Yellowstone River by introducing an
412 open population modeling framework is critical for the management of the fishery and will have
413 implications for trout monitoring throughout Montana.

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420 **Conflict of Interest Statement**

421 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

422 **Data Availability Statement**

423 Data available on request.

424 **Ethics Statement**

425 All work was conducted in accordance with Montana Fish, Wildlife and Parks sampling
426 guidelines.

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Tables

Table 1. Eighty percent quantiles of relative bias for annual abundance (\widehat{N}_t) and apparent survival ($\widehat{\phi}$) for each simulated scenario. Scenarios represent 16 combinations of simulated values of superpopulation size (N), apparent survival (ϕ), and detection probability (p). Ten-year datasets were simulated using the simulated parameter values and a POPAN model was fit to each dataset. Each scenario was simulated for 1000 iterations. Relative bias was calculated for annual abundance and apparent survival for each iteration and summarized by scenario using 10% and 90% quantiles. Scenarios where the 10% and 90% quantiles are > -0.25 and < 0.25 (low relative bias), respectively, are shown in bold.

Scenario	Simulated parameters			Annual abundance \widehat{N}_t		Apparent survival $\widehat{\phi}$	
	N	Median ϕ	Median p	10% quantile	90% quantile	10% quantile	90% quantile
1	10000	0.30	0.10	-0.876	0.418	-0.577	0.820
2	10000	0.30	0.15	-0.505	0.302	-0.413	0.501
3	10000	0.30	0.20	-0.354	0.227	-0.320	0.365
4	10000	0.30	0.25	-0.256	0.195	-0.253	0.293
5	10000	0.70	0.10	-0.620	0.254	-0.303	0.320
6	10000	0.70	0.15	-0.345	0.199	-0.204	0.231
7	10000	0.70	0.20	-0.227	0.161	-0.156	0.177
8	10000	0.70	0.25	-0.165	0.139	-0.126	0.148
9	20000	0.30	0.10	-0.773	0.358	-0.485	0.610
10	20000	0.30	0.15	-0.401	0.263	-0.321	0.407
11	20000	0.30	0.20	-0.280	0.204	-0.243	0.280
12	20000	0.30	0.25	-0.211	0.169	-0.200	0.226
13	20000	0.70	0.10	-0.589	0.260	-0.271	0.299
14	20000	0.70	0.15	-0.318	0.194	-0.186	0.209
15	20000	0.70	0.20	-0.217	0.154	-0.136	0.158
16	20000	0.70	0.25	-0.157	0.131	-0.109	0.132

Table 2. Median standard error for annual abundance (\widehat{N}_t) and apparent survival ($\widehat{\phi}$) for each simulated scenario. Scenarios represent 16 combinations of simulated values of superpopulation size (N), apparent survival (ϕ), and detection probability (p). Ten-year datasets were simulated using the simulated parameter values and a POPAN model was fit to each dataset. Each scenario was simulated for 1000 iterations. The median standard error represents the median value from all iterations for each scenario.

Scenario	Simulated parameters			Annual abundance \widehat{N}_t	Apparent survival $\widehat{\phi}$
	N	Median ϕ	Median p		
1	10000	0.30	0.10	433.1	0.127
2	10000	0.30	0.15	288.2	0.087
3	10000	0.30	0.20	212.8	0.065
4	10000	0.30	0.25	168.2	0.052
5	10000	0.70	0.10	253.5	0.095
6	10000	0.70	0.15	185.7	0.067
7	10000	0.70	0.20	146.5	0.050
8	10000	0.70	0.25	122.3	0.040
9	20000	0.30	0.10	608.3	0.091
10	20000	0.30	0.15	412.2	0.062
11	20000	0.30	0.20	300.8	0.046
12	20000	0.30	0.25	238.4	0.037
13	20000	0.70	0.10	366.4	0.069
14	20000	0.70	0.15	265.2	0.048
15	20000	0.70	0.20	207.9	0.036
16	20000	0.70	0.25	172.2	0.028

Figures

Figure 1. Locations of the Corwin Springs and Mill Creek sampling sites on the upper Yellowstone River, Montana. The enlarged area is denoted by the shaded rectangle in the inset map.

Figure 2. The number of Brown Trout (BT), Rainbow Trout (RT) and Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout (YCT) sampled during three years of electrofishing surveys at two sites in the upper Yellowstone River. Lighter shaded areas at the top of the bars indicate the proportion of fish sampled that were recaptures.

Figure 3. Estimates of (A) detection probability \hat{p} and (B) apparent survival $\hat{\phi}$ from POPAN models for Brown Trout (BT), Rainbow Trout (RT) and Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout (YCT) at two sites in the upper Yellowstone River, Montana. The error bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. Parameters for Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout at Mill Creek were inestimable due to low sample size.

Figure 4. Estimates of annual abundance \widehat{N}_t from POPAN models and Lincoln-Petersen closed population models for three trout species at two sites in the upper Yellowstone River, Montana. The error bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. Parameters for Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout at Mill Creek were inestimable due to low sample size.

Figure 5. Relative bias of (A) annual abundance estimates \widehat{N}_t and (B) apparent survival estimates $\hat{\phi}$ for 16 simulated scenarios. The horizontal dashed lines represent a relative bias of zero. Scenarios represent 16 combinations of simulated values of superpopulation size (N), apparent survival (ϕ), and detection probability (p). Ten-year datasets were simulated using the simulated parameter values and a POPAN model was fit to each dataset. Each scenario was

simulated for 1000 iterations. Relative bias was calculated for annual abundance and apparent survival for each iteration.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Supplemental tables and figures

Table S1. The number of iterations (out of 1000) removed from analysis for each simulated scenario.

Scenario	Simulated parameters			Number of iterations removed
	N	Median Φ	Median p	
1	10000	0.30	0.10	111
2	10000	0.30	0.15	6
3	10000	0.30	0.20	0
4	10000	0.30	0.25	0
5	10000	0.70	0.10	391
6	10000	0.70	0.15	301
7	10000	0.70	0.20	285
8	10000	0.70	0.25	251
9	20000	0.30	0.10	38
10	20000	0.30	0.15	1
11	20000	0.30	0.20	0
12	20000	0.30	0.25	0
13	20000	0.70	0.10	368
14	20000	0.70	0.15	218
15	20000	0.70	0.20	241
16	20000	0.70	0.25	220

Table S2. Eighty percent quantiles of relative bias for superpopulation size (\hat{N}), detection probability (\hat{p}), and probability of entry (\hat{b}). Scenarios represent 16 combinations of simulated values of superpopulation size (N), apparent survival (ϕ), and detection probability (p). Ten-year datasets were simulated using the simulated parameter values and a POPAN model was fit to each dataset. Each scenario was simulated for 1000 iterations. Relative bias was calculated for annual abundance and apparent survival for each iteration and summarized by scenario using 10% and 90% quantiles. Scenarios where the 10% and 90% quantiles are > -0.25 and < 0.25 (low relative bias), respectively, are shown in bold.

Scenario	Simulated parameters			Superpopulation size \hat{N}		Detection \hat{p}		Probability of entry \hat{b}	
	N	Median ϕ	Median p	10% quantile	90% quantile	10% quantile	90% quantile	10% quantile	90% quantile
1	10000	0.30	0.10	-0.283	0.413	-0.378	0.554	-0.482	0.508
2	10000	0.30	0.15	-0.205	0.236	-0.266	0.351	-0.324	0.336
3	10000	0.30	0.20	-0.161	0.154	-0.175	0.257	-0.247	0.251
4	10000	0.30	0.25	-0.112	0.140	-0.154	0.166	-0.201	0.205
9	10000	0.70	0.10	-0.091	0.091	-0.132	0.232	-0.712	0.771
10	10000	0.70	0.15	-0.059	0.062	-0.088	0.138	-0.483	0.533
11	10000	0.70	0.20	-0.042	0.046	-0.085	0.084	-0.376	0.398
12	10000	0.70	0.25	-0.036	0.034	-0.067	0.066	-0.307	0.329
13	20000	0.30	0.10	-0.229	0.284	-0.281	0.456	-0.458	0.472
14	20000	0.30	0.15	-0.138	0.176	-0.187	0.226	-0.302	0.310
15	20000	0.30	0.20	-0.103	0.125	-0.147	0.155	-0.230	0.235
16	20000	0.30	0.25	-0.084	0.094	-0.124	0.126	-0.182	0.186
21	20000	0.70	0.10	-0.075	0.080	-0.108	0.193	-0.679	0.736
22	20000	0.70	0.15	-0.049	0.057	-0.085	0.110	-0.476	0.507
23	20000	0.70	0.20	-0.037	0.040	-0.069	0.076	-0.350	0.373
24	20000	0.70	0.25	-0.028	0.030	-0.059	0.051	-0.289	0.303

Table S3. Median standard error for superpopulation size \hat{N} , detection probability \hat{p} , and probability of entry \hat{b} . Scenarios represent 16 combinations of simulated values of superpopulation size (N), apparent survival (ϕ), and detection probability (p). Ten-year datasets were simulated using the simulated parameter values and a POPAN model was fit to each dataset. Each scenario was simulated for 1000 iterations. The median standard error represents the median value from all iterations for each scenario.

Simulated parameters							
Scenario	N	Median ϕ	Median p	Superpopulation size \hat{N}	Detection \hat{p}	Probability of entry \hat{b}	
1	10000	0.30	0.10	2385.3	0.0305	0.0183	
2	10000	0.30	0.15	1607.9	0.0303	0.0130	
3	10000	0.30	0.20	1165.2	0.0302	0.0100	
4	10000	0.30	0.25	891.5	0.0284	0.0084	
5	10000	0.70	0.10	587.0	0.0093	0.0236	
6	10000	0.70	0.15	385.3	0.0090	0.0175	
7	10000	0.70	0.20	282.2	0.0087	0.0137	
8	10000	0.70	0.25	215.0	0.0083	0.0113	
9	20000	0.30	0.10	3491.7	0.0221	0.0128	
10	20000	0.30	0.15	2295.8	0.0216	0.0091	
11	20000	0.30	0.20	1647.6	0.0210	0.0071	
12	20000	0.30	0.25	1260.1	0.0201	0.0059	
13	20000	0.70	0.10	835.9	0.0065	0.0173	
14	20000	0.70	0.15	549.2	0.0064	0.0125	
15	20000	0.70	0.20	399.6	0.0062	0.0097	
16	20000	0.70	0.25	306.2	0.0059	0.0080	

Supplemental Figures

Figure S1. Length frequency histograms of Brown Trout (BT), Rainbow Trout (RT) and Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout (YCT) sampled during three years of electrofishing surveys at two sites in the upper Yellowstone River.

Figure S2. Estimates of recruitment (including immigration) from POPAN models for Brown Trout (BT), Rainbow Trout (RT) and Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout (YCT) at two sites in the upper Yellowstone River, Montana. The error bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. Parameters for Yellowstone Cutthroat Trout at Mill Creek were inestimable due to low sample size.

Figure S3. Relative bias of superpopulation size \hat{N} for 16 simulated scenarios. The horizontal dashed line represents a relative bias of zero. Scenarios represent 16 combinations of simulated values of superpopulation size (N), apparent survival (ϕ), and detection probability (p). Ten-year datasets were simulated using the simulated parameter values and a POPAN model was fit to each dataset. Each scenario was simulated for 1000 iterations.

Figure S4. Relative bias of detection probability \hat{p} for 16 simulated scenarios. The horizontal dashed line represents a relative bias of zero. Scenarios represent 16 combinations of simulated values of superpopulation size (N), apparent survival (ϕ), and detection probability (p). Ten-year datasets were simulated using the simulated parameter values and a POPAN model was fit to each dataset. Each scenario was simulated for 1000 iterations.

Figure S5. Relative bias of probability of entry \hat{b} for 16 simulated scenarios. The horizontal dashed line represents a relative bias of zero. Scenarios represent 16 combinations of simulated values of superpopulation size (N), apparent survival (ϕ), and detection probability (p). Ten-year datasets were simulated using the simulated parameter values and a POPAN model was fit to each dataset. Each scenario was simulated for 1000 iterations.

Figure S1.

Figure S2.

Figure S3.

Figure S4.

Figure S5.